

A New Glycoside from the Stem of *Nyctanthes arbortristis*

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Manuscript received 21 November 1977, revised 4 May 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

Phytochemical examination of the stem of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* resulted in the isolation and identification of β -sitosterol and a new glycoside naringenin-4'-*o*- β -glucopyranosyl- α -xylopyranoside.

NYCTANTHES arbortristis (N. O. Oleaceae) is reputed for medicinal importance^{1,2}. The chemical examination of the plant was undertaken because a review of the literature revealed that very little work has been done on its leaves³⁻⁶ and seeds⁷ and no work on its stem.

Results and Discussion

The petroleum ether extract of the water insoluble fraction of the ethanolic extract gave a white compound (yield 100 mg) m.p. 135-7°. It was characterized as β -sitosterol by its m.p. colour reactions, R_f value and also by m.m.p. and co-chromatography with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol^{8,9}.

The water soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract was subjected to liquid-liquid extraction with different organic solvents in order of their increasing polarities. The acetone soluble fraction afforded the reported glycoside. It was purified as reddish-brown coloured compound (1.5 g) over a column of silica gel. Acid hydrolysis (7% aqueous H_2SO_4) yielded a yellow-brown coloured aglycone $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$, m.p. 249-51° and two sugars which were characterized as xylose and glucose by co-chromatography with authentic samples and osazone formation. The yellow-brown coloured aglycone was identified as naringenin by its specific colour reactions, m.p., m.m.p., R_f value, (paper chromatography, solvent, *n*-Butanol : 27% aqueous acetic acid 1 : 1, (v/v) $R_f=0.925$, Lit., $R_f=0.925$); spectral analysis (spectral shifts with various complexing reagents), degradation studies and co-chromatography with an authentic sample of naringenin¹⁰.

Periodate oxidation of the glycoside consumed 3.2 moles of periodate with the production of 1.3 moles of formic acid per mole of the glycoside, suggesting the presence of a disaccharide having both the units in pyranose form. Hydrolysis with formic acid confirmed them to be in the form of a disaccharide.

The position of the sugar linkage in the glycoside was determined by comparing the properties of

the glycoside with those of the aglycone. Both the glycoside and the aglycone gave positive colour tests and U.V shifts ($\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-AlCl_3}$; 25 nm and $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-NaOAc}$; 36 nm) for the presence of free hydroxy groups at positions 5 and 7. Thus the only position left for the linkage of sugar to the aglycone is position-4'. This is further supported by the following observations :

1. The aglycone gave a blue colour on addition of sodium bicarbonate solution to the pink solution obtained by the Schinoda reaction while the glycoside did not.
2. The aglycone but not the glycoside gave *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid m.p. 212° (lit m.p. 214°) on oxidation with neutral potassium permanganate and also on degradation with 50% ethanolic potassium hydroxide.

These observations suggested the presence of a free hydroxyl group at position-4' in the aglycone and not in the glycoside. Thus the sugar is linked to the aglycone at position-4'.

The aqueous hydrolysate obtained by partial hydrolysis of the glycoside with 2% sulphuric acid showed first the appearance of glucose, suggesting it to occupy the terminal position in the sugar moiety and xylose is linked glycosidically with the aglycone at position-4'.

The failure of the glycoside to reduce Fehling solution and to give a positive test with aniline hydrogen phthalate reagent indicated that both the sugars are linked through their respective reducing groups. The reducing group at C_1 of xylose is therefore linked to naringenin nucleus and the reducing group at C_1 of glucose is linked to xylose at either C_2 , C_3 or C_4 positions. The permethylated glycoside on acid hydrolysis gave 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose (paper chromatography, solvent *n*-butanol : ethanol : water, 4 : 1 : 5, $R_f=0.84$, lit.=0.85) and 2, 3-di-*o*-methyl-D-xylose, (paper chromatography *n*-butanol : ethanol :

water; 5 : 1 : 4 $R_f=0.73$ lit.=0.74) indicating that the sugars are in pyranose form and the linkage between the two sugars is not 1-2 or 1-3. The following fact further proves that 1-3 linkage is not possible. If the reducing group at C_1 of glucose is linked to the hydroxyl group C_3 of xylose, three vicinal hydroxyls in glucose but none in xylose will be free. Therefore during periodate oxidation two moles of periodate will be consumed with the liberation of one mole of formic acid per mole of the glycoside. On the other hand, if the reducing hydroxyl (C_1) of the glucose is linked to C_4 hydroxyl of xylose, three vicinal hydroxyls in glucose and two in xylose will be free. Under these conditions three moles of periodate will be consumed with the liberation of one mole of formic acid per mole of the glycoside which is in good agreement with the experimental results. Hence glucose and xylose are present as a 1 : 4 bioside and this in turn is linked to the aglycone through the reducing group of xylose. The pyranose structure was also supported by i.r. spectral studies of the glycoside (I.R. peak at 825 cm^{-1})¹¹. The enzymatic hydrolysis of the glycoside showed the β -linkage between the two sugars and the α -linkage between the aglycone and the xylose.

Thus, keeping all the facts together the structure to the glycoside has been assigned as naringenin-4'- β -glucopyranosyl- α -xylopyranoside.

Experimental

The plant material was collected locally and identified by the Botanical Survey of India, Allahabad.

Isolation and Purification :

The air dried powdered stem (2 kg) was refluxed with hot ethanol on a steam bath for 120 hr. The total ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and the concentrate was poured into excess of distilled water with continuous stirring. The water insoluble portion was extracted with petroleum ether in a 250 c.c. round bottomed flask. The petroleum ether extract was chromatographed over neutral alumina. Elution with benzene : chloroform (6 : 4 v/v) gave a compound which was identified as β -sitosterol by the usual tests. The

water soluble fraction was subjected to liquid-liquid extraction using petroleum ether, benzene, ethyl acetate and acetone separately. The acetone soluble fraction when purified over the column of silica gel gave a reddish-brown coloured compound (1.5 g) m.p. $102-3^\circ$. It was found to be a single entity by paper chromatography in *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5 v/v) R_f value=0.50. It gave a pink colour with Mg/HCl, deep red colour with 2 : 4 D.N.P. and a positive Molisch test (Found C, 55.09; H, 5.35; $C_{26}H_{30}O_{14}$; requires C, 55.12; H, 5.30).

Hydrolysis :

The glycoside (500 mg) was hydrolysed with 7% aqueous sulphuric acid for 3 hours. The aglycone was recovered as usual, m.p. $249-51^\circ$ (d) (Found : C, 66.14; H, 4.4; $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$; requires C, 66.17; H, 4.41). The aqueous hydrolysate was found to contain two sugars glucose and xylose (paper chromatography, solvent, *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water 4 : 1 : 5 (v/v), spray Aniline hydrogen phthalate for glucose $R_f=0.18$ and for xylose $R_f=0.27$; authentic glucose $R_f=0.18$, xylose $R_f=0.28$).

Acetylation of Aglycone and Acetyl Percentage Determination :

The aglycone (50 mg) was acetylated by the usual method ($Ac_2O/py.$). The acetyl derivative was crystallized from methanol. It melted at $51-53^\circ$ (lit $53-5^\circ$). The percentage of the acetyl group in the acetylated product was determined by the method of Wisenberger¹² as described by Belcher and Gobert¹³ (Found : $COCH_3$, 32.43%, requires for $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$ ($COCH_3$)₃, - $COCH_3$ 32.41%).

Cleavage of the Aglycone with 50% Ethanolic KOH :

The aglycone (50 mg) was dissolved in the minimum amount of ethanol (10 ml) and refluxed with 15 ml of 50% ethanolic KOH solution at 100° for six hours. It was allowed to cool, acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and shaken with

- (i) 50% $NaHCO_3$, a compound, *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid m.p. 212° (lit. m.p. 214°) was identified in this fraction.
- (ii) 1% NaOH, this fraction gave a compound which was identified as phloroglucinol m.p. 215° (lit. m.p. $217-19^\circ$).

Partial Hydrolysis of the Glycoside :

The glycoside (50 mg) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 2% sulphuric acid. Aliquots were taken out at different intervals and examined by paper chromatography. Glucose showed its appearance after one hour. After two and half hours of hydrolysis xylose appeared.

Hydrolysis of the Glycoside with Formic Acid :

The glycoside (30 mg) was dissolved in boiling cyclohexanol and hydrolysed with formic acid (8 ml, 7%) by refluxing on a water bath for half an hour. The aqueous hydrolysate gave a single spot by paper chromatography. The R_f value of this entity was not found to be identical with the R_f value of various monosaccharides in different solvent systems^{1,4}. Further hydrolysis of this hydrolysate with 7% H_2SO_4 gave glucose and xylose.

Enzymatic Hydrolysis of the Glycoside :

The glycoside (20 mg) was hydrolysed with emulsin prepared from almonds^{1,5} at 30-40° for 72 hours. Liberation of only glucose in the hydrolysate was confirmed by co-chromatography.

Periodate Oxidation of the Glycoside :

The glycoside (20 mg) was dissolved in 25 ml of ethanol and was treated with 25 ml of 0.1M solution of sodium metaperiodate. The periodate consumed and formic acid liberated were titrated by the titrimetric method of Jones *et al*^{1,6}.

Moles of periodate consumed = 3.2
Moles of formic acid liberated = 1.3

Infrared Spectrum of the Glycoside :

The prominent peaks in the i.r. spectrum of the glycoside (in KBr phase) were as follows : 3400, 2945, 1680, 1570, 1520, 1465, 1360, 1275, 1125, 1025, 825 cm^{-1} .

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